

Reconstruction of data regarding the « Reasons for concerns » about climate change from figures in IPCC and related publications

Technical working document

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1. Purpose of this document

This technical document describes the production of the data about burning ember diagrams from IPCC reports and related publications used to build figure 3 of Zommers et al. [1]. The starting point is the burning ember diagrams regarding the Reasons for concerns about climate change provided in the IPCC TAR [2], Smith et al. [3] (for AR4-related embers), AR5 [4] and SR15 [5]. The result is a tabulated evaluation of global mean temperature increases corresponding to each risk level in those diagrams.

An introduction to the approach is provided in section 1 of the Supplementary Information (SI) associated with Zommers et al. [1]. This document provides detailed information on the analysis of the colours within the original figures that was used to reconstruct the « burning embers ». The SI provides the motivation for our approach and documents its limitations; it should thus be read in conjunction with this document.

2. Content of this document

The following pages present the approach and diagrams described in the SI as the “procedure to extract temperature data from the original figures”. For each ember, the colours are plotted against global mean temperature (GMT) increase. Each page relates to one of the original figures. Those figures were used to evaluate the GMT increase corresponding to the colour transitions, and report that evaluation in Excel files (see section 5). On most figures, especially those most used to evaluate GMT increase levels, grey lines are added to help in the process, in relation with the difficulties explained in section 3.

For the TAR, two sources are included: the final SPM and technical summary (TS) as approved by the IPCC Plenary and available on the website of the IPCC (PDF version of the report as available in January 2020). The main source used for Zommers et al. is the approved TS (figure 1). The SPM (figure 2) was plotted for confirmation and for information about colours above the maximum GMT increase in the TS (+5°C above the reference temperature in the TS, while the scale extends above 6°C in the SPM). As noted in the SI [1], there is a third source of information about the TAR: the draft SPM as approved by the WGII Plenary before copy editing and technical adjustments [6]. The relevance of this figure comes from the fact that several reproductions of the TAR embers in reports and publications appear more similar to this version than to the final version approved by the IPCC Plenary (this was the final approval step, in April 2001, while the WGII Plenary was in February 2001). However, we did not include this version in the analysis presented here to avoid the potential confusion that may arise from including a draft. Besides, we think that comparing this ‘WGII Plenary’ version to the final would not benefit from converting it to numerical data and reconstructing it as we are doing here: given that the two original figures share the same layout, it is at least as useful to compare them directly.

For AR5, we used the version of the embers in “printing colours” (cyan, magenta, yellow, black, i.e. CMYK, a subtractive colour model) as provided in chapter 19 of the report (figure 4 of this document). A conversion to “screen colours” (red, green blue, i.e. RGB, the standard additive colour model) was performed for information (figure 5 of this document), as previous embers were produced with this mode of colour representation.

3. Difficulties involved in the reproduction of the RFC « embers »

Several technical aspects of the original figure complicate the evaluation of a level of warming corresponding to each level of risk. While the general concept and risk scale was maintained across reports, there are some small changes. Here we want to have a table of numbers representing the link between warming and risk which can then be processed in the same way for all embers to produce diagrams that closely reproduce the original ones. Due to the slight technical differences between reports and other difficulties, some assumptions and approximations are needed:

- In the IPCC TAR and Smith et al. (2009), the temperature-scales appear « non-linear »: the distance on paper between -0.6 and 0°C is more than 60% of the distance between 0 and 1°C. This was fixed by assuming that there are two scales: below and above 0°C (/ « recent » global mean temperature). In our data, we only use one linear scale, so data read below 0°C is converted using a rule of

thumb, such as

final-temp = value-read / 0,85 [= difference to pre-ind. on the « linear scale » used above 0°C]
* 0,6 [= actual difference between recent and pre-ind. temperatures]

(so a read value of - 0.85 translates to - 0.6°C, which is what is intended = the pre-industrial level, w.r.t. 'recent' temperatures in the TAR).

- the TAR includes 3 « blurred starts of colour transitions » for unique systems, extremes, and large discontinuities. For those three transitions, the colour changes are not linear but rather « slowly starting », with continuous first derivatives of their colour changes vs T (no « broken lines », see plots on the following pages). It is not the case for the 2 other embers (distribution and aggregated). This thus appear intentional. However, we have the impression that the human eye can hardly see that detail, and it is not found in recent embers (see SR15 in this document). It could be implemented in software to reproduce embers, but this is not done here, as the added value of this complexity does not appear evident.

To approach human perception of the « end of colour transition », we often used a linear extrapolation of the colour changes towards the end of transitions (see graphs). This is done manually rather than by software, but we think that a more sophisticated analysis, although possible, would not provide more « accurate » values :

(1) some form of linear fit would still imply arbitrary choices (e.g. should the whole range of the transition be used or just its ends?) and (2) one has to remember that there was no intention, when those figures were build, to provide precise thresholds (see main text in Zommers et al. [1]), thus trying to get extremely precise details appears useless - beyond the already precise information obtained here.

- In Smith et al (2009), but not in the TAR and mostly not in AR5, the scale includes « light red » in between the yellow and red colours (within the « transition »); this is further explained in figure 3. Note that there is no explicit « colour scale » in Smith et al 2019 and earlier embers.

4. *Technical aspects of our analysis*

In addition to the above difficulties related to the original figures, there are a few practical aspects of interest to understand the colour vs. temperature diagrams presented in the following pages and the resulting reconstruction of the embers data:

- The colour density axis has a reversed scale, so that for example RGB = 0,0,0 is white (RGB being an additive colour system, it should be 1,1,1, while 0,0,0,0 is white in CMYK). This has no influence on the results.
- The location of each ember within the image files were collected manually and stored in a file that is available on request (« BE-analysis-fig-data »). Those files were processed by a python script (« ReadEmber-2019.py ») based on the PIL image library [7], resulting in the graphs provided in the following pages.
- When differences are seen between the following curves and what « appear » on the screen, they may be associated with colour profiles, defined or not defined in the files and taken into account or not by the viewing software, as well as screen calibration, especially if a RGB version is compared to a CMYK version.

5. *Resulting data and reproduction of the figures*

Using the analysis of the colours shown in figures 1 to 6, we evaluated the global mean temperature increases corresponding to the changes in risk: the start of the transition from white to yellow, the end of this transition (= full yellow), the start of the transition from yellow to red... When the middle of a transition (50% colour change, or 'median' point) was located substantially away from the mean temperature, we provided a GMT value for this risk midpoint. As explained in the SI [1], and given the difficulties and technical considerations above, there is no unambiguous way to generate such data: independent reproductions of this exercise may result in differences by at least ~0.1°C. We considered both the functions describing the amount of each colour as functions of temperature and the original diagram.

The resulting Excel file is provided with the “Ember factory” online application which can build the ember diagram on this basis: <https://climrisk.org/emberfactory/examples#Z2020>. The application is available with an open-source licence (GNU-GPL 3).

The file is named RFCs-data-2020_01_26-Z2020_rev1.xlsx. When submitting this file to the application, the result is a reproduction of figure 3 in Zommers et al. [1], i.e. embers collected by reason for concern and presented to illustrate the change from one report to the next. It is also possible to group the embers in panels corresponding to each original report. This only requires a change in graphic parameters, as provided in the file RFCs-data-2020_01_26-Z2020_rev1_byPubli.xlsx.

Figure 7 provides a comparison between the embers reconstructed from our approach and the original figures.

References

1. Zommers, Z., Marbaix P, Fischlin A., Ibrahim Z. Z., Grant Z, Magnan A. K., Pörtner H-O, Howden M., Calvin K., Warner K., Thiery W., Sebesvari Z., Davin E. L., Evans J.P., Rosenzweig, C., O'Neill B. C., Anand Patwardhan, Warren R., van Aalst M. K. and Hulbert M., *Burning Embers: Towards more transparent and robust climate change risk assessments*. Accepted for publication in *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*
2. McCarthy, J. J.; Canziani, O. F.; Leary, N. A.; Dokken, D. J.; and White, K. S. (ed.), *Climate Change 2001: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability, Contribution of Working Group II to the Third Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, Cambridge University Press (2001). ISBN 0-521-80768-9
3. Smith, J. B., S. H. Schneider, M. Oppenheimer, G. W. Yohe, W. Hare, M. D. Mastrandrea, A. Patwardhan, et al. « Assessing Dangerous Climate Change through an Update of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) “Reasons for Concern” ». *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* (2009). doi:10.1073/pnas.0812355106.
4. IPCC, 2014: *Summary for policymakers. In: Climate Change 2014: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Part A: Global and Sectoral Aspects. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Field, C.B., V.R. Barros, D.J. Dokken, K.J. Mach, M.D. Mastrandrea, T.E. Bilir, M. Chatterjee, K.L. Ebi, Y.O. Estrada, R.C. Genova, B. Girma, E.S. Kissel, A.N. Levy, S. MacCracken, P.R. Mastrandrea, and L.L. White (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, pp. 1-32. <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar5/wg2/>
5. IPCC, 2018: *Summary for Policymakers. In: Global Warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change, sustainable development, and efforts to eradicate poverty* [Masson-Delmotte, V., P. Zhai, H.-O. Pörtner, D. Roberts, J. Skea, P.R. Shukla, A. Pirani, W. Moufouma-Okia, C. Péan, R. Pidcock, S. Connors, J.B.R. Matthews, Y. Chen, X. Zhou, M.I. Gomis, E. Lonnoy, T. Maycock, M. Tignor, and T. Waterfield (eds.)]. In Press. <https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/chapter/spm/>
6. Summary for Policymakers. *Climate Change 2001: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Approved by IPCC Working Group II in Geneva, 13-16 February 2001. Draft (19 February 2001)*. This document was made public by the IPCC WGII but is no longer available on the website of the IPCC to our knowledge. Retrieved from <https://web.archive.org/web/20031020230620/http://www.ipcc.ch/wg2SPM.pdf> in July 2020.
7. More precisely the Pillow fork: <https://python-pillow.org>

Figure 2

TAR (SPM)

Aggregate impacts

Large scale discontinuities

Figure 3

Smith et al.
2009: 'AR4'

Note : The end of the transition « to red » includes colors that are not expected in a linear change from yellow to red: the last change is a change from « pale red » to « more intense red » (= result of the simultaneous decrease in blue and green). This limits the possibility to fully compare to other embers, because the color *scale* is different (not just the levels). However, this is hardly visible and thus of limited importance.

Figure 4

AR5 (ch19)

Figure 5

AR5 (ch19)
same source as
previous page,
converted to RGB

Figure 6

SR15

Figure 7: comparison of the reproduced embers to the original figures (the reproduced embers are identical to figure 3 in Zommers et al. [1], with additional lines to facilitate the comparison and a grouping by report)

